

Susceptibility of some cereal crops to cyst nematode *Heterodera sacchari* in West Africa

D.L. Coyne, Natural Resources Institute, Chatham Maritime, Kent ME4 4TB, and R.A. Plowright, CABI Bioscience, Bakeham Lane, Egham, Surrey TW20 9TY, UK E-mail: dannycoyne@compuserve.com

The sugarcane cyst nematode, *Heterodera sacchari*, is a parasite of rice throughout West Africa (e.g., Babatola 1984, Coyne 1999). In Nigeria, it is considered potentially important on rice (Babatola 1984). Babatola (1983) demonstrated its high pathogenicity on susceptible upland rice in pots. Cropping systems in West Africa are diverse, reflecting the low-input management systems of subsistence farmers, who produce the majority of rice. Maize, sorghum, and millet are commonly intercropped, relay-cropped, or cultivated in rotation with rice. The host status of these crops for *H. sacchari* is unknown.

Two seeds of local varieties of maize, millet, and sorghum and of a susceptible rice check (IDSA6) were sown in steam-sterilized sandy soil (9% clay, 15% silt, 75% sand) in 8-L plastic pots. Seedlings were thinned to 1 pot⁻¹ at emergence. The experiment was arranged on benches in the screenhouse in a completely randomized design with five replications. Treatments comprised uninoculated controls and 200 cysts pot⁻¹ (25 cysts L⁻¹ soil). Cysts were derived from mature IDSA6 plant roots following several generations in pots in a screenhouse. Inoculum was mixed into the upper 5 L of soil by hand prior to sowing.

At harvest, plant height, grain weight, cyst density in soil, and mean number of eggs per cyst were determined.

Leaf dry weight was measured after oven-drying and root fresh weight was recorded after rinsing each root system and dabbing it dry. All data were analyzed using ANOVA.

Each crop in the study was susceptible to *H. sacchari* (see table). Cyst number pot⁻¹ increased in all crops, although significantly larger populations developed on rice. The fecundity of cysts on sorghum and maize was lower than on either rice or millet.

Cereal crops commonly cultivated in cropping systems with rice in West Africa were poor hosts of *H. sacchari*. The multiplication factor (Pf:Pi, final cyst population:initial cyst population) indicated that total egg populations declined on each cereal host. Although the decline was greatest on sorghum, the reduced root weight in inoculated pots shows that sorghum was not resistant to *H. sacchari*. Each crop supported some cyst production, suggesting that each would maintain *H. sacchari* in the soil.

The occurrence of cysts with eggs on these crops may indicate variability in virulence within the inoculum. Hence, selection for ability to multiply on poor hosts may occur in later generations. Intercropping, relay, or rotation cropping of maize, sorghum, or millet with rice is likely to reduce this selection pressure. It is also likely that such cropping practices would not lead to higher *H. sacchari*

population densities on rice. Multiple cropping, if carefully managed, would more likely provide some level of control of *H. sacchari* in rice. Such a practice can suppress the development of nematode populations that are more capable of reproducing on a susceptible crop or cultivar (Wallace et al 1995). Practices that are implemented to manage one nematode should not, however, encourage the development of other potential pest nematodes. For instance, intercropped maize may facilitate the buildup of *Pratylenchus zaei* around rice roots (Coyne et al 1998).

References

- Babatola JO. 1983. Pathogenicity of *Heterodera sacchari* on rice. *Nematol. Mediterr.* 11:21–25.
- Babatola JO. 1984. Rice nematode problems in Nigeria: their occurrence, distribution and pathogenesis. *Trop. Pest Manage.* 30(3):256–265.
- Coyne DL. 1999. Epidemiology and crop loss assessment of rice nematodes in West Africa. PhD thesis, University of Reading, UK. 213 p.
- Coyne DL, Ndongidila A, Oyediran I, Heinrichs EA, Plowright RA. 1998. *Pratylenchus zaei* in upland rice as influenced by the ratio of intercropped maize. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 23(3):27–28.
- Wallace MK, Orf H, Steintra WC. 1995. Field population dynamics of soybean cyst nematode on resistant and susceptible soybeans and their blends. *Crop Sci.* 35:703–707.

Susceptibility of maize, millet, sorghum, and rice in sandy soil to *Heterodera sacchari*.^a

Crop	Pi (cysts L ⁻¹ soil)	Height (mm)	RFW (g)	LDW (g)	Grain weight (g)	Pf (cysts L ⁻¹ soil)	Pf (eggs cyst ⁻¹)	Pf:Pi cysts	Pf:Pi eggs ^b
Maize	0	1,584	19.8	18.3	–	–	–	–	–
	25	1,512	17.2	16.9	–	80.0	13.8	3.2	0.28
Sorghum	0	2,103	14.8	14.9	1.9	–	–	–	–
	25	1,941	8.8**	14.0	1.6	45.6	6.5	1.8	1.07
Millet	0	1,828	13.4	32.3	4.3	–	–	–	–
	25	1,597	7.5	23.1*	4.0	31.2	90.0	1.2	0.71
Rice (IDSA6)	0	948	14.0	9.3	3.5	–	–	–	–
	25	712*	5.2***	4.3**	1.6*	760.0	157.0	30.4	30.40
LSD (P = 0.05)		–	–	–	–	185.2	57.7	–	–

^aRFW = root fresh weight, LDW = leaf dry weight, Pf = final cyst population density, Pi = initial cyst population density. ^bAssuming that egg content of cysts at inoculation was the same as at harvest (i.e., 157 eggs cyst⁻¹). *, **, *** = means significantly different from that of uninoculated control at P = 0.05, P = 0.01, and P = 0.001, respectively.